

EFFICIENT WEED MANAGEMENT IN CHICKPEA (*Cicer arietinum* L.) THROUGH NEW GENERATION HERBICIDES

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Abstract

An experiment entitled "Efficient weed management in chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) through new generation herbicides" was implemented at Agricultural Research Station, Badnapur, Dist. Jalna (MS) during rabi, 2022. Experiment was laid out in randomized block design comprising twelve treatments with three replications. Among the different weed control treatments, grain yield and stover yield was highest with weed free treatment (T_{12}) and it was found at par with Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + quizalofop-p-ethyl 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post) (T_8), Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + propaquizafop 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post) (T_9) and Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + topramezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14-21 DAS (pre+post) (T_{10}). Similar results were found in case of gross and net monetary returns. Whereas, the treatment Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + topramezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14-21 DAS (pre+post) (T_{10}) numerically recorded maximum value of B: C ratio followed by the treatment Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + propaquizafop 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post) (T_9) and the treatment weed free (T_{12}).

Keywords: Post-emergence, pre-emergence, grain yield, stover yield and economics

Introduction

Chickpea plays a major role in enhancing soil fertility through their nitrogen-fixing capacity. It can fix up to 140 kg N ha⁻¹ in a growing period (Poonia and Pithia, 2013) [6]. It adds plenty of organic matter for maintaining and improving soil health and fertility. It leaves a considerable amount of residual nitrogen for subsequent crops. It has been distinguished into two categories based on seed characteristics, the 'Desi' types, with relatively small, angular seeds with a rough texture and the 'Kabuli' types, which are larger, rounded and cream-colored seeds.

India contributes 70% of the total world chickpea production of 116.2 lakh tonnes cultivated fewer than 112 lakh hectares with a productivity of 1036 kg ha⁻¹ in 2020-21 (Anonymous, 2021) [1]. In chickpea weeds emerge and grow rapidly in many flushes. In the legumes principally in the case of chickpea, pendimethalin @ 1000 g ha⁻¹ applied as pre-emergence is a very typical herbicide that is used to control all types of weeds, but there are no herbicides available to apply as post-emergence to control the emerging BLWs effectively. Even if the pre-emergence application of herbicide is missed due to any reason, in that case, post-emergence herbicide application to control the grassy, as well as non-grassy weeds, is very much required. Hand weeding has been found very effective but the shortage of labor when there is a need and at more rates has become a serious question. The chickpea, in spite of the fact that it is an important rabi pulse crop yet no required information on efficient weed management, is available. So, the application of individual herbicide alone is not much more effective and economical weed control measures under such conditions. In the current time, some of the very effective high-potential herbicide molecules have been evolved which may be useful to limit the wide spectrum weed infestation in chickpea. Further, if these molecules are used in a mixture may be more effective to control the wide spectrum of weeds. Herbicide combinations will assist the farmers for efficient weed control. Henceforth, weed management studies are required to evaluate the different herbicide combinations aiming for wide spectrum weed control as well as reducing the herbicide doses. It makes better weed control practices that comprise chemical weed control with newer formulations and herbicide blends. The assumption is that weeds can be controlled effectively and yield is maintained with lower rate of input practices by the improved weed management strategy.

Material and Methods

The field experiment was conducted in the rabi season of the year, 2022. Climatologically, this area falls in the semi-arid region. The total rainfall received during the year 2022 was 889 mm distributed

in 51 rainy days against the normal average rainfall of 630 mm in 42 rainy days. Experiment consisted of twelve treatments laid out in randomized block design with three replications. The treatments consist with oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha (pre-emergence) (T_1), oxyfluorfen 250 g a.i./ha (pre-emergence) (T_2), quizalofop-p-ethyl 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (post-emergence) (T_3), propaquizafop 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (post-emergence) (T_4), topramezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14 DAS (post-emergence) (T_5), topramezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 21 DAS (post-emergence) (T_6), topramezone 25.7 g a.i./ha at 21 DAS (post-emergence) (T_7), oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha fb quizalofop-p-ethyl 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS pre+post) (T_8), oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha fb propaquizafop 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post) (T_9), oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha fb topramezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14-21 DAS (pre+post) (T_{10}), weedy check (T_{11}) and weed free check (T_{12}). The chickpea variety BDNG-797 was sown on 3rd November, 2022 at spacing of 30 x 10 cm² using seed rate 70 kg ha⁻¹. The fertilizer was applied as per the recommended dose to chickpea crop as 25:50:00 kg NPK ha⁻¹. The required quantity of herbicides viz., propaquizafop, oxyfluorfen, quizalofop-p-ethyl and topramezone was measured by weighing balance and measuring cylinder at the time of preparation of solution according to treatments. The spraying was done by using knapsack sprayer with flat fan nozzle using 500 liters of water ha⁻¹. The crop was grown with recommended package of practices and was harvested at maturity on 16th March 2023. A statistical method of analysis of variance and interpretation of data as suggested by (Panse and Sukhatme, 1985) [5], for randomized block design. Standard error of mean (SEM) was worked out for each factor. Whenever the results were significant, the critical difference (C.D.) at 5 per cent level of significance were worked out.

Results and Discussion**Effect of weed management treatments on growth and yield attributes**

The ancillary data presented in Table 1 revealed that significantly lower plant height was recorded by unweeded plot than herbicide treated and weed free plots. Significantly highest plant height of chickpea was observed by the treatment weed free (T_{12}) and it was found at par with Topramezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14 DAS (post-emergence) (T_5), Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + quizalofop-p-ethyl 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post) (T_8), Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + propaquizafop 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post) (T_9) and Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + topramezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14-21 DAS (pre+post) (T_{10}), respectively. Maximum number of branches plant⁻¹ were recorded by the weed free treatment (T_{12}) which was comparable with Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + quizalofop-p-ethyl 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post) (T_8), Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha +

propaquizafop 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post) (T₉) and Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + topramezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14-21 DAS (pre+post) (T₁₀), respectively. Similar trend was observed in respect of seed index. The weed free treatment (T₁₂) recorded significantly higher number of pods plant⁻¹, however, it was on par with Topramezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14 DAS (post-emergence) (T₅), Topramezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 21 DAS (post-emergence) (T₆), Topramezone 25.7 g a.i./ha at 21 DAS (post-emergence) (T₇), Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + quizalofop-p-ethyl 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20

DAS (pre+post) (T₈), Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + propaquizafop 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post) (T₉) and Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + topramezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14-21 DAS (pre+post) (T₁₀). The better growth and yield attributes observed due to combination of Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha with topramezone 20.6 g a.i./ha or propaquizafop 100 g a.i./ha and alone application of topramezone 20.6 g a.i./ha might be attributed to better weed control over alone application of Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha, propaquizafop 100 g a.i./ha or quizalofop-p-ethyl 100 g a.i./ha.

Table 1: Growth and yield attributes of chickpea as affected by new generation herbicides

Tr. no	Treatments	Growth and yield attributes			
		Plant height (cm)	No. of branches Plant ⁻¹	No. of pods Plant ⁻¹	Seed index (g)
T ₁	Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha (pre-emergence)	32.73	4.33	35.73	20.83
T ₂	Oxyfluorfen 250 g a.i./ha (pre-emergence)	34.90	4.70	41.80	21.10
T ₃	Quizalofop-p-ethyl 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (post-emergence)	33.53	4.27	39.30	21.33
T ₄	Propaquizafop 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (post-emergence)	35.67	4.70	43.13	21.67
T ₅	Topramezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14 DAS (post-emergence)	37.03	5.93	47.27	21.43
T ₆	Topramezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 21 DAS (post-emergence)	36.57	5.77	46.47	21.77
T ₇	Topramezone 25.7 g a.i./ha at 21 DAS (post-emergence)	36.10	5.53	45.70	21.67
T ₈	Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + quizalofop-p-ethyl 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post)	38.33	6.03	50.33	23.00
T ₉	Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + propaquizafop 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post)	39.53	6.33	51.33	23.33
T ₁₀	Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + topramezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14-21 DAS (pre+post)	40.87	6.53	53.13	23.67
T ₁₁	Weedy check	29.87	4.07	32.90	19.67
T ₁₂	Weed free check	43.80	6.87	56.00	24.60
	SE ±	2.44	0.37	3.62	0.58
	CD 5%	7.18	1.08	10.63	1.69
	CV%	11.59	11.79	13.87	4.54
	G. Mean	36.58	5.42	45.26	22.01

Effect of weed management treatments on seed yield, stover yield and harvest index

The data presented in Table 2 showed significant differences in seed yield of chickpea due to different new generation herbicides. Weed free treatment recorded significantly higher seed yield of chickpea than the rest of the treatments, however, it was found at par with Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + quizalofop-p-ethyl 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post) (T₈), Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + propaquizafop 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post) (T₉) and Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + topramezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14-21 DAS (pre+post) (T₁₀). The lowest seed yield was recorded by the weedy check treatment. Highest stover yield was recorded by the treatment weed free (T₁₂), which was found to be on par with the treatment Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + propaquizafop 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post) (T₉) and Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + topramezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14-21 DAS (pre+post) (T₁₀) and significantly superior over rest of the treatments. Numerically, highest value of Harvest Index was recorded by the treatment weed free (T₁₂) followed by the treatment

Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + topramezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14-21 DAS (pre+post) (T₁₀), Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + propaquizafop 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post) (T₉) and Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + quizalofop-p-ethyl 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post) (T₈) with general mean of 41.70 %. Among the different weed control practices used in the experiment, application of pre-emergence herbicide followed by post emergence herbicide treatment was found significantly better than application of pre-emergence herbicide only or post-emergence herbicide only in respect of grain and stover yield of chickpea. This might be due to better weed management resulting in improvement in all growth and sink parameters which contributed higher yield owing to favourable condition in absorbing soil moisture, nutrient content and sunlight penetration during crop growing period. The grain and stover yield were significantly lowest under weedy check treatment. These results correlate with the findings of (Chaithanya, et al., 2021), (Deepika, et al., 2021) and (Sanketh, et al., 2021) [2], [3] and [7].

Table 2: Seed yield (Kg ha⁻¹), Stover yield (Kg ha⁻¹) and harvest index (%) of Chickpea as influenced by new generation herbicides

Tr. no	Treatments	Seed Yield (Kg ha ⁻¹)	Stover Yield (Kg ha ⁻¹)	Harvest Index (%)
T ₁	Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha (pre-emergence)	1440	2079	40.84
T ₂	Oxyfluorfen 250 g a.i./ha (pre-emergence)	1595	2229	41.69
T ₃	Quizalofop-p-ethyl 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (post-emergence)	1489	2127	41.03
T ₄	Propaquizafop 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (post-emergence)	1623	2235	42.01
T ₅	Topramezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14 DAS (post-emergence)	1724	2364	42.12
T ₆	Topramezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 21 DAS (post-emergence)	1656	2287	41.99
T ₇	Topramezone 25.7 g a.i./ha at 21 DAS (post-emergence)	1610	2242	41.79
T ₈	Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + quizalofop-p-ethyl 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post)	1808	2444	42.48

T ₉	Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + propaquizafop 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post)	1831	2475	42.51
T ₁₀	Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + topamezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14-21 DAS (pre+post)	1899	2549	42.65
T ₁₁	Weedy check	1102	1720	38.94
T ₁₂	Weed free check	2136	2863	42.68
	SE ±	115.84	142.41	-
	CD 5%	339.77	417.70	-
	CV%	12.09	10.72	-
	G. Mean	1659	2301	41.70

Effect of different weed management practices on economics of chickpea

In case of Gross Monetary Returns (GMR), highest value was recorded by the treatment weed free (T₁₂) and was found to be at par with Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + quizalofop-p-ethyl 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post) (T₈), Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + propaquizafop 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post) (T₉) and Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + topamezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14-21 DAS (pre+post) (T₁₀). The lowest value of gross monetary returns was

Table 3: Gross monetary returns (Rs ha⁻¹), Net monetary returns (Rs ha⁻¹) and B: C ratio of Chickpea as influenced by new generation herbicides.

Tr no	Treatments	Economics		
		GMR (Rs ha ⁻¹)	NMR (Rs ha ⁻¹)	B:C ratio
T ₁	Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha (pre-emergence)	71275	34827	1.96
T ₂	Oxyfluorfen 250 g a.i./ha (pre-emergence)	78817	40963	2.08
T ₃	Quizalofop-p-ethyl 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (post-emergence)	73683	35821	1.95
T ₄	Propaquizafop 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (post-emergence)	80135	42533	2.13
T ₅	Topamezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14 DAS (post-emergence)	85109	45035	2.12
T ₆	Topamezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 21 DAS (post-emergence)	81773	41939	2.05
T ₇	Topamezone 25.7 g a.i./ha at 21 DAS (post-emergence)	79528	38973	1.96
T ₈	Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + quizalofop-p-ethyl 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post)	89155	48886	2.21
T ₉	Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + propaquizafop 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post)	90307	50685	2.01
T ₁₀	Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + topamezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14-21 DAS (pre+post)	93638	51660	2.23
T ₁₁	Weedy check	54824	20850	1.61
T ₁₂	Weed free check	105319	56167	2.14
	SE ±	5590.32	5590.32	-
	CD 5%	16396.80	16396.80	-
	CV%	11.81	20.57	-
	G. Mean	81964	42362	2.04

Conclusion

Among the different weed control treatments weed free treatment provides more consistent weed control than the other method of weed management. Amongst weed management practices, application of pre-emergence herbicide *i.e.*, oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha followed by application of post-emergence herbicides *i.e.*, topamezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14-21 DAS provided more consistent weed control than the other method of weed management. This kept the weeds in control and resulted in producing a maximum yield of chickpea crop. From the economic point of view application of pre-emergence herbicide *i.e.* oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha followed by application of post-emergence herbicides *i.e.* topamezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14-21 DAS proved economically viable treatment based on B: C ratio amongst various weed management treatments.

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recorded by the weedy check treatment. Similar trend was observed in case of net monetary returns. Whereas, the treatment Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + topamezone 20.6 g a.i./ha at 14-21 DAS (pre+post) (T₁₀) numerically recorded highest value of B: C ratio followed by the treatment Oxyfluorfen 150 g a.i./ha + propaquizafop 100 g a.i./ha at 15-20 DAS (pre+post) (T₉) and the weed free treatment (T₁₂). These results corroborate with the findings of (Thakare et al., 2015), (Kakade et al., 2020), (Deepika, et al., 2021) and (Sanketh, et al., 2021) [8]. [4]. [3] and [7].

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